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Research Article

PERCEPTION OF HOUSE OFFICERS ABOUT THEIR PREPAREDNESS FOR CLINICAL PRACTICE: A CROSS- SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract:

Objective: The fundamental aim of any primary medical educational programme is to adequately prepare medical students for clinical practice. Concerns have been growing about whether the fresh graduated medical students are ready to start their work as a clinician or not. The medical graduating vary in their preparedness for their first exposure towards clinical work as house officers. This study aimed to review whether they perceived themselves as being well prepared for clinical practice or not.

Study Design: Observational descriptive cross-sectional survey study

Place & Duration Of Study: It was a one month study carried out during the month of June 2018 in Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore.

Methodology: Using convenient sampling technique, a population of 100 doctors was selected. A self-designed questionnaire consisting of 10 questions was administered and participants were asked to indicate to what extent they agreed or disagreed with the statements. The data was analysed using SPSS-22 software.

Result: The overall response rate was 95%(95/100).The house officers felt well prepared with regards to history taking, physical examination skills, proper counselling of patients, various clinical procedures and application of medical ethics into clinical practice. On the other hand, they felt deficiencies in the diagnoses and effective management of acute and chronic disorders as well as prescription of safe medicine in medical and surgical emergencies. Majority of them were not satisfied with the current clinical learning methods at their respective medical schools and suggested that the learning strategies be changed. They felt that their responsibility as a house officer exceeded their capability also that they were not being provided proper guidance by their supervisors.

Conclusion: The house officers felt prepared in some domains of clinical practice whilst felt shortcomings in others. It is surely incumbent upon the concerned medical educators to look for a way whereby these learning deficiencies can be mitigated and the situation be taken care of. Within some limitations and constraints, students must be provided with the opportunity to make proper meaningful contributions towards the patient management, as perceived preparedness is crucial and it influences the behaviour of fresh medical graduates and therefore warrants careful consideration.

Key Words: perceived preparedness, house officers, clinical practice.

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INTRODUCTION:

The main goal of any medical teaching institute and eventually the successful completion of medical education should ensure provision of such knowledge and skills to medical graduates which are necessary for them to become professionally sound young clinicians and work efficiently in the hospitals they are providing their services to [1]. The development of competent health professionals is extremely important, which can be achieved only through introduction of specific effective academic programs, provision of professional support and by giving clinical training in practical form during the undergraduate years [2].

There are strong evidences that newly qualified doctors do not feel prepared to start their work [3]. The transition from medical student to a practicing young clinician is a very important period international research confirms that this transition is frequently experienced as extremely stressful [4]. If the young clinicians are not groomed properly in under graduate education period, it may lead to poor quality of patient care [5]. Crucial factors that influence the young medical graduates' or the young clinician's preparedness may involve both the personal factors (related to the student) as well as the organizational factors (related to the teaching institute or the Teaching Hospital. These include insight into one's level of neuroticism and building up of confidence, effective educational learning environment at their medical school, provision of adequate knowledge and practical skills, integration of basic science knowledge with clinical practice and presence of supervisor support [6, 7].

The foremost duty of a young clinician is to properly cater for the needs of patients, take detailed history of the illness they are suffering from, reach to an appropriate diagnosis by applying the required examination skills ordering lab test thereafter manage and treat the patient appropriately [8]. On the other hand, a young doctor is usually the first person with whom a patient arriving in the emergency department

encounters. Therefore the capability of a doctor to handle acute emergencies, be it medical or surgical, is very critical and is a matter of great concern as the doctor stands on the line separating life and death of the patient. So, the complete knowledge to recognize acutely ill patients and the need to generate early resuscitation is essential for newly qualified doctors [9]. In addition to this, Physical examination skills and clinical procedures are also the fundamental learning objectives to be achieved by a young doctor and the right approach towards a patient marks them as a professionally competent health care providers. Also, the prescription of effective medicine to a patient at the right time with adequate dosage for proper duration is of great importance in medical practice. The prescribed medicine should have a high safety profile and should be cost effective meeting the desired needs of the patient [10]. The ability of a doctor to counsel a patient regarding the patient's condition and its management plays an important role not only in coping with the patient's illness but also their reservations regarding effective treatment. This also helps in building the trust of the patients on their doctors [11]. Furthermore, applying medical ethics into clinical practice is important and is part of the curriculum of all medical institutes now a day. [12].

Lastly, having a professionally competent and concerned supervisor, who properly guides the trainee doctors, plays a positive role in development of their clinical as well as professional skills [13]. All these domains must be taken care of by a newly qualified doctor as part of his/her duty as a house officer or an intern. But unfortunately, they feel shortcomings in few or most of these areas and believe that these deficiencies be rectified.

Not being able to fulfil the criteria of a professionally can lead to major degree of stress, low confidence and low self-esteem [14]. To check for competencies of doctors, formal assessments to determine range of skill competencies in workplace ought to be done [15]. It is very important to investigate the level of preparedness

of a young doctor will help in generating an effective healthcare unit.

The present study was conducted to look upon the perceived preparedness of the young doctors to carry out their clinical work effectively. The study was in Sir Ganga Ram Hospital which is a tertiary care unit and the teaching hospital of Fatimah Jinnah Medical University (FJMU). The study reviewed the opinion of the house officers regarding their preparedness for the clinical practice with regards to their medical knowledge and the acquisition of various clinical skills required during House Job. The main objective of the study was to assess the self-perceived preparedness of the house-officers for their clinical practice as well as to identify the concerned areas of deficiency with the aim to provide necessary improvements.

METHODOLOGY:

This was a one month observational descriptive cross-sectional study carried out from 1st June to 30th June in the year 2018. The study population comprised of newly appointed house officers in various departments of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. In this hospital, every year, more than 250 fresh graduates from Fatima Jinnah Medical University as well as other medical institutions throughout the country receive their foundation year training which is known as house-job training in the country. The departments include the department of Medicine, Surgery, Ophthalmology, Otorhinolaryngology, Anesthesia, Urology,

Nephrology, Cardiology, Psychiatry, Dermatology, Pediatrics, Obstetrics and Gynecology etc. In the present study, all the young doctors inducted as house officers were fresh graduates of the Year 2018 who completed their undergraduate medical training from Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore. Using convenient sampling technique, a self-designed questionnaire was distributed amongst hundred house officers. The questionnaire comprised of 10 questions to assess their self-preparedness. A 5-point Likert scale was used and the participants were asked to mention indicate to what extent they agreed or disagreed with the statements ranging from strongly disagree, disagree, uncertain, agree and strongly agree (scored as 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 respectively). All the participants were informed about the objectives of the study. After informed consent, the questionnaires were filled by the participants. The completed questionnaires were collected by the investigators. The data was entered and analysis was done using SPSS 22 software.

RESULTS:

The overall response rate was 95 % (95/100). The mean age of the respondents was 24.213 years.

The percentage of marks in the last professional examination scored by the young doctors after the completion the last year of their medical school is given in Graph # 1. The percentage distribution of house officers in different departments is given in table # 1 and graph # 2.

Graph # 1 - Percentage of Marks in Last Professional Examination

Graph # 2 – Distribution of Respondents in Clinical Departments

Table # 1 - Distribution of Respondents in Clinical Departments

CLINICAL DEPARTMENT	NUMBER (PERCENTAGE)
Department of Medicine	61 (70.52%)
Department of Surgery	14 (14.73%)
Surgical Allied	
Ophthalmology	4 (4.21%)
Otorhinolaryngology	2 (2.10 %)
Anesthesia	2 (2.10%)
Medical Allied	
Psychiatry	1 (1.05%)
Dermatology	1 (1.05%)
Pediatrics	1 (1.05%)
Obstetrics & Gynecology	19 (20%)

The responses given for each of the 10 questions is given in table # 2. The mean scores in each domain are given in table # 3

Table # 2 – Responses to the Questions

QUESTIONS	STRONGLY AGREE	AGREE	UNCERTAIN	DISAGREE	STRONGLY DISAGREE
Management of Clinical Cases With Regards To Medical Knowledge	0	20	26	42	7
Physical Examination Skills And Clinical Procedures	21	62	7	4	1
Application of Medical Ethics In Clinical Practice.	17	46	24	7	1
Prescription of Safe Medicine	59	3	14	17	2
Diagnosis And Management of Acute Cases	1	24	28	42	0
Properly Counselling of A Patient	31	46	10	6	2
Satisfaction With Current Learning Environment	15	0	11	34	35
Satisfaction With Current Learning Method & Learning Strategies	5	1	6	43	40
Responsibilities Exceed Capabilities	38	36	8	7	6
Proper Guidance By Seniors/Supervisors	10	9	12	36	28

Table # 3 – Individual Mean Scores of the Questions with Standard Deviations

QUESTION	MEAN+-SD
Management of Clinical Cases With Regards To Medical Knowledge	2.140 ± 0.683
Physical Examination Skills And Clinical Procedures	2.53 ± 0.70
Application of Medical Ethics In Clinical Practice.	2.27 ± 0.79
Prescription of Safe Medicine	2.48 ± 0.83
Diagnosis And Management of Acute Cases	2.14 ± 0.83
Properly Counselling of A Patient	2.95 ± 0.98
Satisfaction With Current Learning Environment	1.46 ± 1.08
Satisfaction With Current Learning Method & Learning Strategies	1.23 ± 0.98
Responsibilities Exceed Capabilities	2.48 ± 1.55
Proper Guidance By Seniors/Supervisors	1.77 ± 1.46

DISCUSSION:

The main aim of any medical school is to adequately prepare its medical students for clinical practice. Numerous studies have identified a perception among

fresh medical graduates that they are unprepared for their role as junior doctors. There are many evidences showing that this lack of self-confidence is not global, rather, it is mainly concentrated in few of the areas.

These are the areas which need improvement for the optimum development of young clinicians [2]. This study was carried out to find the gaps in the preparation of young doctors for their clinical work. Our findings confirmed that the newly qualified doctors felt prepared in some areas while unprepared in other areas of practice.

Physical Examination Skills and Clinical Procedures:

More than 80% of medical graduates felt well prepared with regards to physical examination skills and clinical procedures giving a mean score of 2.53 ± 0.70 . During clinical years of medical training, the supervising doctors teach them physical examination skills which are necessary for the properly diagnosing a patient and subsequently providing the right care and management. Clinical procedures should be properly learnt and a medical undergraduate should have a strong grip on them. The clinical procedures include passing endotracheal tube, nasogastric tube insertion intravenous cannulation, arterial and venous sampling etc. it is vitally important as these are the foremost duties that a young clinician is required to perform. Performance of numerous procedures are required which need mastery of not only technical skills but non-technical skills too. It's an unfortunate finding that formal assessment of these skills is lacking during the course of undergraduate clinical training. There is a need to develop and implement assessment programs like PS-OSCE (Procedural Skill-Objective Structured Clinical Examination) for students as well as interns [16].

Properly Counselling Of a Patient:

Another domain in which the young doctors felt well prepared was the art of properly counselling a patient. 77% strongly agreed/agreed with the statement that they possessed this art of counselling a patient properly. Patient counselling is one of the most important tools for better and optimum clinical care. Counselling involves properly educating a patient with the aim to increase knowledge about the healthcare issues faced by him/her. It also involves the provision of details about the treatment for the disease suffered by the patient including complete information of possible benefits and harms the treatment carries [16, 17].

Application of Medical Ethics in Clinical Practice:

63% of young doctors felt that they were able to apply medical ethics into clinical practice with only 8% disagreeing with the statement. Medical ethics education is becoming an integral part of medicine programme as more and more emphasis is being

placed on professional behavior of the doctors [19]. There is utmost need for analyzing the current state of education and implementation of medical ethics in the country's hospitals, placing a major particular focus on the essential role played by it in the cultivation of professionalism among the learners of medical field [20].

Prescription of Safe Medicine:

59% of the house officers strongly agreed that they could safely prescribe medicine to the patient, with only 2% strongly disagreeing with it. Prescribing medicine to the patients is a big step up from being just a learning medical student to becoming a practicing doctor. A large percentage of graduates of medical schools around the world do not feel well prepared for it which is evident from the researches carried out in this domain [20]. Doctors in the United Kingdom are of the opinion that the prescription of the right medicine to the right patient is a major skill that ought to be learnt by the medical students during their learning years, but unfortunately they were not receiving hands-on training and experience as a student [21, 22]

Newly qualified junior doctors, working in various departments of the hospital, have the responsibility of prescribing safe drugs to diseased patients. Thus, the prescription of right drug to them, which has a high safety profile and cost effectiveness, is a huge concern for the hospital and patient care [23]

Proper Guidance by Seniors/Supervisors:

Proper guidance by the supervisor is important in enhancing the clinical performance. Unfortunately, 74% of the respondents felt that they were not being properly guided by their supervisors. Research shows that the newly qualified young doctors are facing problems regarding when to ask for help from senior supervising doctors because of various reasons, the foremost being the fear of getting scolded by them [24].

The management of patients in a hospital setting is a very complex inter-professional process and it involves a higher possibility of errors. It is therefore the foremost duty of the supervisors to guide the young doctors, who are under their supervision, properly. This way many avoidable errors shall be taken care of and the provision of optimal patient care be made possible [25].

Diagnosis and Management of Acute Cases:

Only 25 % agreed that they could diagnose and manage acute emergencies one of the fundamentals

that is included in the training of Young doctors is their proper preparation for handling acute cases and further providing emergency care to high risk collapsing patients presenting in the emergency department. Acute emergencies like acute myocardial infarction, diabetic ketoacidosis, acute asthma, acute renal failure etc. are few of the acute emergencies encountered on daily basis in medical emergency room and it is an absolute requirement from the young junior doctors that they be able to provide quality care to these acutely ill patients. Clinical training should put more emphasis on management of acutely ill patients and also on enhancing their ability to provide early resuscitation as an essential part of learning and practice of all newly qualified doctors [26, 27, 28].

Management of Clinical Cases With Regards To Medical Knowledge:

None of the respondents strongly agreed with this statement that they could manage clinical cases with regard to medical knowledge, only 20% agreed with it while more than 75% disagreed with it according to research on newly inducted interns, 1 in 10 of the fresh graduating medical doctor felt unprepared to manage the clinical scenarios that they encountered in practice [29].

It extremely essential that medical students be exposed to such environment where they can easily correlate their basic science knowledge with clinical practice. There is a need of provision of more structured clinical placements in different ward in the teaching hospitals to prepare them for clinical work. This will be a major gateway to reduce the stress of transition [30, 31].

Satisfaction with Current Learning Method & Learning Strategies:

Very poor score was seen in this domain and only 6% agreed that they were satisfied with the current learning methods and the strategies followed by the trainers. Adequate amendments should be made in the curriculum to ensure optimal education and the required clinical experience of fresh medical graduates to make them professionally competent doctors. Structurally designed clinical learning methods play a crucial role in developing and polishing the practical skills of medical graduates. If proper learning strategies are not followed by the concerned educators, it may lead to hazardous consequences in the form of mal-practicing clinicians which may lead to improper patient care [32].

Satisfaction with Current Learning Environment:

Only 15% were totally satisfied with their current learning environment. It can be easily appreciated that

the educational environment is the soul and spirit of medical curriculum. A proper learning environment plays a crucial role in formulation of professional doctors. The aim of any medical school must be to provide a better stable and supportive educational environment. There is a strong and positive relationship of medical graduates' preparedness of all clinical areas with the learning environment provided to them [33, 34, 35]

Responsibilities Exceed Capabilities:

74% of the respondents agreed that their responsibilities exceeded their capabilities. This is an alarming situation as it may eventually badly affect their function as health care provider. There is no doubt that transition from student to a professional young doctor is a huge leap in terms of responsibilities. For many graduates the main stress-provoking issues are related to coping up with this higher level of responsibility as well as uncertainty followed by it [36, 37].

Research shows that majority of the young doctors experienced situations when they felt over-burdened as well as fearful about having to take the responsibility for major decisions related to the patients' hospital care. It was further revealed that they came to realization that they were ultimately responsible for the lives of the patients and this pressure of actually dealing with the life of the patient was found as extremely challenging [38].

CONCLUSION:

The house officers felt prepared in some domains of clinical practice whilst they felt shortcomings in others. Majority of the young doctors felt unprepared and unable to cope up with the responsibility of clinical practice as well as faced shortcomings in their clinical learning experience and their preparedness to manage patients on their own. The transition from being a medical student to a professional practicing doctor will always be stressful followed by uncertainty as it is a life changing step in the early career of a young doctor. The medical educationists, however, should take an insight into this matter to ensure development of competent health professionals. It is surely incumbent upon the concerned them to look for ways whereby these deficiencies can be mitigated and the situation be taken care of. Within some limitations and constraints, students must be provided with the opportunity to make proper meaningful contributions towards the patient management, as perceived preparedness is crucial and it influences the behavior of fresh medical graduates and therefore warrants careful consideration.

REFERENCES:

1. Ochsmann EB, Zier U, Drexler H, Schmid K. Well prepared for work? Junior doctors' self-assessment after medical education. *BMC medical education*. 2011 Dec;11(1):99.
2. Simpson JG, Furnace J, Crosby J, Cumming AD, Evans PA, David MF, Harden RM, Lloyd D, McKenzie H, McLachlan JC, McPhate GF. The Scottish doctor--learning outcomes for the medical undergraduate in Scotland: a foundation for competent and reflective practitioners. *Medical teacher*. 2002 Jan 1;24(2):136-43.
3. Kellett J, Papageorgiou A, Cavenagh P, Salter C, Miles S, Leinster SJ. The preparedness of newly qualified doctors--Views of Foundation doctors and supervisors. *Medical teacher*. 2015 Oct 3;37(10):949-54.
4. Dyrbye L, Shanafelt T. A narrative review on burnout experienced by medical students and residents. *Medical education*. 2016 Jan;50(1):132-49.
5. Boamah SA, Laschinger H. The influence of areas of worklife fit and work-life interference on burnout and turnover intentions among new graduate nurses. *Journal of Nursing Management*. 2016 Mar;24(2):E164-74.
6. Daud MR, Chan LC, Taib F. Medical Students' Preparedness as Junior Doctors on Palliative Care Issues: A Single Centre Study. *Education in Medicine Journal*. 2016 Apr 1;8(2).
7. Borggreve AS, Meijer JM, Schreuder HW, Ten Cate O. Simulation-based trauma education for medical students: a review of literature. *Medical teacher*. 2017 Jun 3;39(6):631-8.
8. Sadler DR. Three in-course assessment reforms to improve higher education learning outcomes. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*. 2016 Oct 2;41(7):1081-99.
9. Hall MA, Orentlicher D, Bobinski MA, Bagley N, Cohen IG. Health care law and ethics. *Wolters Kluwer Law & Business*; 2018 Feb 26.
10. Hill-Taylor B, Walsh KA, Stewart S, Hayden J, Byrne S, Sketris IS. Effectiveness of the STOPP/START (Screening Tool of Older Persons' potentially inappropriate Prescriptions/Screening Tool to Alert doctors to the Right Treatment) criteria: systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled studies. *Journal of clinical pharmacy and therapeutics*. 2016 Apr;41(2):158-69.
11. Cruess RL, Cruess SR, Steinert Y, editors. *Teaching medical professionalism: supporting the development of a professional identity*. Cambridge University Press; 2016 Mar 29.
12. Thomas PA, Kern DE, Hughes MT, Chen BY, editors. *Curriculum development for medical education: a six-step approach*. JHU Press; 2016 Jan 29.
13. De Lasson L, Just E, Stegeager N, Malling B. Professional identity formation in the transition from medical school to working life: a qualitative study of group-coaching courses for junior doctors. *BMC medical education*. 2016 Dec;16(1):165.
14. McCranie EW, Brandsma JM. Personality antecedents of burnout among middle-aged physicians. *Behavioral Medicine*. 1988 Mar 1;14(1):30-6.
15. Sadler DR. Three in-course assessment reforms to improve higher education learning outcomes. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*. 2016 Oct 2;41(7):1081-99.
16. Pugh D, Hamstra SJ, Wood TJ, Humphrey-Murto S, Touchie C, Yudkowsky R, Bordage G. A procedural skills OSCE: assessing technical and non-technical skills of internal medicine residents. *Advances in Health Sciences Education*. 2015 Mar 1;20(1):85-100.
17. Wilson-Barnett J. Patient teaching or patient counselling?. *Journal of advanced nursing*. 1988 Mar;13(2):215-22.
18. Hawton K, McKeown S, Day A, Martin P, O'Connor M, Yule J. Evaluation of out-patient counselling compared with general practitioner care following overdoses. *Psychological medicine*. 1987 Aug;17(3):751-61
19. Harris J. *The value of life: an introduction to medical ethics*. Routledge; 2006 Dec 5.
20. Gillon R. Medical ethics: four principles plus attention to scope. *Bmj*. 1994 Jul 16;309(6948):184.
21. Harding S, Britten N, Bristow D. The performance of junior doctors in applying clinical pharmacology knowledge and prescribing skills to standardized clinical cases. *British journal of clinical pharmacology*. 2010 Jun 1;69(6):598-606.
22. Tully MP, Ashcroft DM, Dornan T, Lewis PJ, Taylor D, Wass V. The causes of and factors associated with prescribing errors in hospital inpatients. *Drug safety*. 2009 Oct 1;32(10):819-36.
23. Guthrie B, McCowan C, Davey P, Simpson CR, Dreischulte T, Barnett K. High risk prescribing in primary care patients particularly vulnerable to adverse drug events: cross sectional population database analysis in Scottish general practice. *Bmj*. 2011 Jun 21;342:d3514.

24. Clayton J, Butow P, Tattersall M, Chye R, Noel M, Davis JM, Glare P. Asking questions can help: development and preliminary evaluation of a question prompt list for palliative care patients. *British journal of cancer*. 2003 Nov 25;89(11):2069.
25. Chassin MR, Loeb JM. High-reliability health care: getting there from here. *The Milbank Quarterly*. 2013 Sep;91(3):459-90.
26. Weaver WD, Sutherland K, Wirkus MJ, Bachman R. Emergency medical care requirements for large public assemblies and a new strategy for managing cardiac arrest in this setting. *Annals of emergency medicine*. 1989 Feb 1;18(2):155-60.
27. Soar J, Pumphrey R, Cant A, Clarke S, Corbett A, Dawson P, Ewan P, Foëx B, Gabbott D, Griffiths M, Hall J. Emergency treatment of anaphylactic reactions—guidelines for healthcare providers. *Resuscitation*. 2008 May 1;77(2):157-69.
28. Waeckerle JF. Disaster planning and response. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 1991 Mar 21;324(12):815-21.
29. Blumenthal D, Gokhale M, Campbell EG, Weissman JS. Preparedness for clinical practice: reports of graduating residents at academic health centers. *Jama*. 2001 Sep 5;286(9):1027-34.
30. Corlett J, Palfreyman JW, Staines HJ, Marr H. Factors influencing theoretical knowledge and practical skill acquisition in student nurses: an empirical experiment. *Nurse education today*. 2003 Apr 1;23(3):183-90.
31. Saarikoski M, Warne T, Aunio R, Leino-Kilpi H. Group supervision in facilitating learning and teaching in mental health clinical placements: a case example of one student group. *Issues in Mental Health Nursing*. 2006 Jan 1;27(3):273-85.
32. Williams NA, Bland W, Christie G. Improving student achievement and satisfaction by adopting a blended learning approach to inorganic chemistry. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*. 2008;9(1):43-50.
33. Liu M, Horton L, Olmanson J, Toprac P. A study of learning and motivation in a new media enriched environment for middle school science. *Educational technology research and development*. 2011 Apr 1;59(2):249-65.
34. Marshall RE. Measuring the medical school learning environment. *Journal of Medical Education*. 1978 Feb;53(2):98-104.
35. Abraham R, Ramnarayan K, Vinod P, Torke S. Students' perceptions of learning environment in an Indian medical school. *BMC medical education*. 2008 Dec;8(1):20.
36. Prince KJ, Van de Wiel M, Van der Vleuten C, Boshuizen H, Scherpbier AJ. Junior doctors' opinions about the transition from medical school to clinical practice: a change of environment. *EDUCATION FOR HEALTH-ABINGDON-CARFAX PUBLISHING LIMITED-*. 2004 Nov;17:323-31.
37. Weller JM, Barrow M, Gasquoine S. Interprofessional collaboration among junior doctors and nurses in the hospital setting. *Medical education*. 2011 May;45(5):478-87.
38. Markwell AL, Wainer Z. The health and wellbeing of junior doctors: insights from a national survey. *Medical Journal of Australia*. 2009 Oct;191(8):441-4.